

Research Article

Verification of the closed loop current controls of Rotor & Grid side converter (RSC & GSC) model of DFIG based Wind Turbine

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Abstract: The close loop current control consists coupling terms with PI regulator in d & q component of the current. All these current loops based on reference transformation (like $DQ-abc$) so on & Phase locked loop so on, that is quit complex thing can be make accurately model as transfer function of second order. The current control model will be compared to the equivalent closed loop current control transfer function by applying the second order system. By this technique, easily can be calculated PI regulator control gain. Then apply the unitary step response for comparing the result between the current control loop & equivalent current control transfer function. Finally, we will be applied the inverse-Laplace transform, where the dynamic behavior is given by natural frequency into the exponential term.

Keyword: PI regulator, Current control Loop, Second order transfer function, Unitary step response & Inverse Laplace Transform.

A. Introduction

Nowadays doubly fed induction generator based wind turbine are mostly used to generate the electricity throughout of the world because it is nature friendly, not have harmful effect on nature, cost effective & its efficiency is more excellent than others generator. Stator and Rotor are the two parts of doubly fed induction generator, stator is directly connected to the grid & rotor is partially connected to the grid through the back to back (Power Electronics) converter to the grid which one is Rotor Side converter & another is Grid Side Converter. Both side

converters have a control system that is Rotor & Grid side converter control [1, 2 & 3]. The common thing of the rotor & grid side converter controls is the current control loop [4 & 5]. In this paper, these current loops will be simplified by closed loop second order transfer function. Both sides converter control inside construction are quite complex thing because it consists of PI regulator in the d & q component of the current with coupling terms & Phase locked loop so on, can be make accurate model as second order transfer function.

The factor of the output to input of the linear system it's called transfer function [6 & 7]. In our model current control loop almost analogous of both side converters, only difference in impedance & resistance like L_r , R_r & L_g , R_g are for the rotor & grid side converter respectively. Since both side current control loops are almost same so here represents the general form of Resistance & Inductance (R, L)[8]

The mathematical term, this current loops general simplified can be found equivalent standard denominator of the second order system, the simplified term of the denominator of the second order system have a damping factor ξ (zeta) . In our model has been used critical damping like $\xi = 1$. After that comparing the two second order system closed loop transfer model to get PI Regulator current control gain (K_p & K_i). Then apply the unitary step response for comparing the result between the current control loop & equivalent current control transfer function. Finally, we will be applied the inverse Laplace transform, where the dynamic behavior is given by natural frequency into the exponential term. After using Laplace transform will get two term, in general, 1st term is responsible for the another shoot at the dynamic response when apply unitary step response & depending how much is the difference between 1st term. This difference means how big the amplitude. This overshoot could be bigger or smaller.

Materials and methods

B. Second order current control close loop of RSC & GSC

The closed loop RSC behave is simplified way as a second order transfer function with a zero & two poles. The close loop current control consists coupling terms with PI regulator in d&q component of the current (Fig. 2).

All these current loops (Fig. 1) based on reference transformation (like DQ-abc)soon & Phase locked loop so on, that is quit complex thing can be make accurately model as transfer function of second order.

The RSC current control loops which these parts together with Phase locked loop that can be simplified to represent & quit accurately as this transfer function the d & q current loops are the same.

Fig. 1. DFIG Rotor side current control loop

Fig. 2. Equivalent closed Current control loop include PI regulators of RSC

In the same way, in GSC current loops can be simplified d & q current loops to transfer function of 2nd order system with a zero & two poles (Fig. 3)

Fig. 3 Grid Side Converter Current Control loop of DFIG

For analyzing the closed current control loops in more generic way need to realize the behavior of transfer function of Rotor & grid side converter. Now here will show the general form of the current control closed loops second order close loop system after that illustrate the details current control loops of RSC & GSC.

$$\frac{i_{ds}(s)}{i_{qs}(s)} = \frac{i_{dr}(s)}{i_{qr}(s)} = \frac{\frac{(k_p s + k_i)}{L}}{s^2 + \left(\frac{k_p + R}{L}\right)s + \frac{k_i}{L}} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where, L & R are the general inductance & resistance of RSC & GSC.

This is current loops general simplified of can found equivalent standard denominator of the second order system.

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} \frac{i(s)}{i^*(s)} &= \frac{\frac{(k_p s + k_i)}{L}}{s^2 + 2\xi\omega_n s + \omega_n^2} \dots\dots\dots (2) & [\xi = 1] \\ &= \frac{\frac{(k_p s + k_i)}{L}}{(s + \omega_n)^2} \end{aligned} \right.$$

Where, Damping factor/ratio, ξ (zita), ω_n = Natural frequency

So, we get k_p & k_i value from equations (1) & (2)

$$k_p = 2\omega_n L - R \text{ \& } k_i = \omega_n^2 L \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where, k_p & K_i is the control gain of the Proportion & integral (PI) regulator

Unitary Unit response

$$i(s) = \frac{(k_p s + k_i)}{s(s + \omega_n)^2}$$

$$i(s) = \frac{k_p}{(s + \omega_n)^2} + \frac{k_i}{s(s + \omega_n)^2} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Now applying the inverse Laplace in equation (4)

$$i(t) = \frac{k_p}{L} t e^{-\omega_n t} + \frac{k_i}{L \omega_n^2} (1 - e^{-\omega_n t} - \omega_n e^{-\omega_n t}) \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

& achieve the temporal current in function of time.

$$i(t) = \frac{1}{L} \left(k_p - \frac{k_i}{\omega_n} \right) t e^{-\omega_n t} + \frac{k_i}{L \omega_n^2} (1 - e^{-\omega_n t}) \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

Steady state condition, $e^{-\omega_n t} = 0$ so,

$$i(t) = \frac{k_i}{L \omega_n^2} = \frac{\omega_n^2 L}{L \omega_n^2} = 1. \quad [k_i = \omega_n^2 L]$$

Where dynamic behavior is given by ω_n in these exponential term ($e^{-\omega_n t}$). In General, this term $\left(k_p - \frac{k_i}{\omega_n} \right) t e^{-\omega_n t}$ is responsible for the another shoot at the dynamic response when apply unitary step response & depending how much is the difference between 1st term $\left(k_p - \frac{k_i}{\omega_n} \right)$ of equation (5). This difference means how big the amplitude. This overshoot ($e^{-\omega_n t}$) could be bigger or smaller.

Fig: 4 Equivalent closed Current control loop include PI regulators of GSC

C. Step Response & Bode Diagram (RSC & GSC)

When amplitude is more than 1 that term is called overshoot. For RSC, at time 0.02s it reaches steady state condition but for GSC it reaches steady state at time 0.015s. Basically it is real pole dynamic system.

(a)

(b)

Fig: 5. Step response of Rotor & grid side converter control (a, b)

Bode Diagram:

This is the close loop behavior of the current loop grid & rotor side converter with the band width very similar.

Fig: 6. Bode diagram of Rode & grid side converter at blue & orange lines respectively

D. Understanding the current regulator error for the digital delay

In Fig. 7 the black line is the voltage references (Sinusoidal reference voltage), they are changing over the time. Here have sampling that measurement of the current then algorithm needs some times to do calculation & once finish the calculation then PWM output is perform just one sample period later in the next triangular. This is one delay that is considered between the RSC / GSC controller & PWM based on the sampled current with 1.5 sampling interval like $1.5T_{sw}$.

During the sampling interval of the synchronous rotating reference frame is simultaneously to the outputs of PI regulator current. Current will be sampled at the beginning time 't' & the algorithm of regulator is accomplished from the beginning time 't'. 1st sampling period 't' convert to $t + T_{sw}$. Then the up-to-date Signals of PWM are operated for subsequent sampling period like $t + T_{sw}$ to $t + 2T_{sw}$. During the algorithm the rotating synchronous reference frame rotates ϑ to $\vartheta + T_{sw}\omega$ where ω is the constant synchronous speed. The average voltage is:

$$V_{dqs}^* = \frac{1}{T_{sw}} \int_{T_{sw}}^{2T_{sw}} V^* e^{j(\tau\omega + \vartheta)} d\tau$$

$$V_{dqs}^* = k(\omega, T_{sw}) * V^* e^{j(1.5\omega T_{sw} + \vartheta)}$$

Fig: 7. Sampling Current & PWM Time Outline.

Fig: 8. Synchronous rotor reference frame as time passes

For these terms $k(\omega, T_{sw})$ & $1.5\omega T_{sw}$ magnitude & phase angle error has been occurred respectively. These errors can be minimized by production of the minimization function.

$$1.5\omega T_{sw} * e^{j(1.5\omega T_{sw})}$$

$$1.5\omega T_{sw} * e^{j(1.5\omega T_{sw})}$$

Sampling frequency, $f_{sw} = \frac{1}{T_{sw}}$, magnitude error is negligible because it is less than 5% whereas, Phase angle error is considered because its angle error is 27 degree at $f = f_{sw}/20$ that is degraded the current regulator performance.

E. Simulation result of current loop (RSC& GSC)

In this case switching frequency 4KHz, this delay hasat the between the control and modulation is not so big, no need to bigger but just in case need to communicate lower switching frequency. It should do it in order to more accurate with the theoretical dynamic response that is predicted so the step has been made and new steady state has been reached.

Fig. 9. Simulation result of current control loop validation of Rotor side converter

Fig: 10. Simulation result of current control loop validation of Grid side converter

F. Conclusion

In this paper has been try to show that our system model is accurate by comparing between the current control model & equivalent closed loop current control of the second order transfer system of the both side converter control (Rotor & Grid side converter control). The closed loop RSC behave is simplified way as a second order transfer function with a zero & two poles. Easily find the PI current regulator gain by applying the second order transfer function. To compensate the current regulator error for digital delay using the compensation. Here have sampling that measurement of the current then algorithm needs some times to do calculation & once finish the calculation then PWM output is perform just one sample period later in the next triangular. This is one delay that is considered between the RSC / GSC controller & PWM based on the sampled

current with 1.5 sampling interval. Finally got the more accurate result by evaluating the current control loop by second order transfer function.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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